

عورتوں کے معاشی اور سماجی حقوق، اسلام اور شریعت کے نظر میں

Journal of Quranic
and Social Studies
01-10

Women's economic and social rights in the context of Islam and Sharia law.

© The Author (s) 2023
Volume:3, Issue: I, 2023

DOI:

www.jqss.org

OJS PKP
OPEN JOURNAL SYSTEMS PUBLIC KNOWLEDGE PROJECT

Nahida Jamal

M.Phil Scholar, Department of Islamic Studies, University of Balochistan, Quetta.

Dr. Sana Jadoon

Assistant in Education Department, Government of Balochistan

Abstract

Islam is a religion that showed immense gratitude towards women. rescued them from the depths of humiliation and degradation, when they were at their lowest point. and the acceptance of their existence was being denied. then the noble prophet, peace be upon him, came as a Blessing to all mankind, and saved humanity from the clutches of the fire and rescued women from that pit. he granted boundless rights to the woman, who were buried alive and bestowed upon them countless privileges in social life. the importance of women in family and societal life should be acknowledged, and responsibilities should be entrusted to them according to their nature. on other hand Western civilization also grants some rights to women, but it is not based on their status. However, the noble Prophet, peace be upon him, grants all the respect and rights to women based on their status alone. He bestows upon them all the dignity and rights that they deserve, regardless of whether they choose to fulfil societal responsibilities or not. after a period of debate, scrutiny, and protest, the current era acknowledged some fundamental rights of women, and this recognition is considered an accomplishment of this era. since this recognition belongs to Islam, it first granted women the rights from which they had been deprived for a long time. Islam did not grant these rights because women demanded them, but because these were inherent rights of women, that they deserved to have. Islam has established the position and status of women in society, which is free from both modern and ancient oppressive customs. it neither allows the objectification of women nor permits them to be unjustly oppressed, and it is not dependent on any freedom attained by Europe.

Keywords: Women's, Economic and Social Rights, Sharia law. Islam, Responsibilities.

Corresponding Author Email:

[ORCID: https://orcid.org/0009-0006-3340-4687](https://orcid.org/0009-0006-3340-4687)

sanajadoon062@gmail.com